

Figure 6: Synergistic cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited NK cells and RIG-I stimulation is independent of donor/tumor KIR-matching.

(a) Schematic representation of the KIR-match and KIR-mismatch (KIR MM) definition used, and table of KIR and their ligands. Based on the NK-cell KIR expression and education status of the NK donors (if the ligand for the KIR is also present on the NK donor), and the HLA-I (KIR ligand) present in the target cells we defined 1. KIR Match: NK cells expressing all HLA-I present on the target and at least one KIR for each of the HLA-I ligands. 2. KIR MM: NK cells with at least 2 KIR/HLA-I combinations for which the ligands are absent on target cells. (b) Cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited primary NK cells with KIR match, or mismatch in the NK donor during 20 h cocultures with Capan-2 (n=5 donors with KIR match, and n=5 donors with KIR MM) and A431 (n=4 donors with KIR match, and n=4 donors with KIR MM). (c) Cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited primary NK cells with KIR matches or mismatches in the NK donor during 20 h-cocultures with target cells previously stimulated with 0.4 μ g/ml RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA). Capan-2, n=4 donors with KIR match, and n=5 donors with KIR MM. A-431, n=4 donors with KIR match, and n=4 donors with KIR MM. Statistical comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šídák's multiple comparisons test (b), or Tukey's post-hoc test (c). *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.